

INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE AND STRESS COPING STYLES OF NEWLY HIRED SECONDARY TEACHERS IN RELATION TO WORK PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

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Instructional Competence and Stress Coping Styles of Newly Hired Secondary Teachers in Relation to Work Performance: Basis for Capacity Development Program

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Abstract

This study examined the instructional competence level of newly-hired public school teachers, the stress coping styles used while teaching, and whether their work performance during the school year 2022-23 changed based on their instructional competence and stress coping styles as the basis for capacity development programs. According to some studies, regardless of their years of experience, teachers of all grade levels are highly susceptible to experiencing work-related stress and being diagnosed with burnout syndrome. The participants of this study are the newly-hired teachers of the municipalities of Pulupandan, Valladolid, San Enrique, and Pontevedra of Division of Negros Occidental. The study employed a descriptive correlational design. It was used to describe the level of instructional competence, stress-coping styles, and work performance of newly-hired teachers when taken as a whole. This study also used the quantitative descriptive design utilizing the survey method through survey questionnaires. In this study, respondents answered questions through questionnaires. The first instrument was adapted from the study of Lebeco (2022) for the Work Instructional Competence, and a modified questionnaire for Stress Coping Styles was used which had undergone validity and reliability properly validated by experts. The respondents are asked to rate each of these parts using a five-point Likert-type scale. The interpretation of passive emotional thinking as very low suggests that the respondents seek help or find people with whom they can share their sentiments about stress. This is a great way of dealing with problems related to their nature of work as newly hired educators. Strategies can be employed to strengthen the respondents' stress-coping styles. As there is a significant relationship between stress coping styles and work performance, the findings do pertain to healthy stress coping styles, which can positively affect one's work performance. Thus, it is necessary to continuously nurture healthy stress-coping habits.

Keywords: *instructional competence, stress-coping styles, newly-hired secondary teachers*

Introduction

The Department of Education's (DepEd) flagship program is the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, or R.A. 10533. The curriculum caters to 21st-century education (DepEd, 2018). However, 21st-century education promises translational and transformative change; therefore, the misinterpreted problem in the nation's educational system needs to be corrected and reembraced for the current generation and beyond. The Philippine educational system is moving away from the traditional teaching concept and toward a direct learning strategy, as we are required to teach 21st-century learners primarily focused on problem-solving, communication, and higher-order thinking skills. According to DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2020, it stresses that teachers' competencies have significantly impacted students' academic performance. Sultan and Shafi (2019) explain competencies as self-evident qualities or properties inexorable for instructing experts to create a favorable climate for persuading students. These are concerned with areas of learners' behavior that are basic for teachers to shoulder prime obligations. Before the current demands of 21st-century education, and in order for the country to be empowered in terms of global competitiveness, there is a need to fill the gap, if any, in teachers' instructional competencies and students' academic performances – and what purports effective teaching.

Many studies conducted during the last few years have shown that teaching is one of the most challenging professions due to the constant expectations and duties it entails (Kidger, 2021). Regardless of their years of experience, teachers of all grade levels are highly susceptible to experiencing work-related stress and being diagnosed with burnout syndrome. In the early years of their teaching professions, newly hired teachers are more likely to be vulnerable and to resign from their positions or choose to move voluntarily to another school (Harmsen, 2019).

Before the pandemic, roughly 20-50% of teachers are known to report more elevated levels of work-related stress than other occupations (Stapleton et al., 2020). Coping styles are vital to dealing with prolonged stress and have meaningful implications for a teacher's physiological and psychological well-being (Stapleton et al., 2020). When teachers utilize poor coping styles, it often leads to burnout, which leads to them leaving the profession entirely.

According to Popescu, Cirja, and Duminica (2019), 30% of novice teachers in England leave the profession within five years. They never return due to the high-stress levels they experience on the job, such as student misbehavior, too many tasks, and lack of support from the administration. Research shows that this is similar in many countries worldwide (Popescu et al., 2019).

This study was concerned with determining the instructional competence of newly-hired public school teachers in the 4th District, mainly because the teachers are in charge of the facilitation of the students' learning experiences and how the instructional competencies and their stress coping styles will bring efficiency and effectiveness to the students. Hence, the advocacy to promote academic excellence and quality education in the Schools Division of Negros Occidental from the standpoint of making this Schools Division a

center of academic excellence made the researcher decide to conduct the study, which determined the instructional competence of newly-hired public school teachers, the stress coping styles, and the input for a proposed capacity development program.

Research Questions

This study's concept is anchored on teachers' stress-coping styles. Its goal is to deeply understand the level of instructional competence of newly hired public school teachers and whether their work performance changes based on their instructional competence and stress-coping styles during school year 2022-23 as the basis for capacity development programs. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of newly hired public school teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. age;
 - 1.3. marital status;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.5. length of service?
2. What is the level of instructional competence of the respondents when taken as a whole and in terms of the following areas:
 - 2.1. lesson planning;
 - 2.2. delivery;
 - 2.3. evaluation of students' performance; and
 - 2.4. classroom management?
3. What is the level of stress coping styles of the respondents?
4. What is the level of work performance of the respondents when grouped according to the aforementioned variables?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of instructional competence of teachers in terms of the demographic profile?
6. Is there a significant difference in the level of stress coping styles of teachers based on the demographic profile?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the instructional competence and the work performance of the newly-hired secondary school teachers?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the stress coping styles and the work performance?
9. Based on the result of the study, what capacity development programs can be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This research aimed to determine the instructional competence and stress coping styles in relation to work performance of secondary public schools' newly-hired teachers of the municipalities of Pulupandan, Valladolid, San Enrique, and Pontevedra under the Division of Negros Occidental. This research employed a descriptive correlational design. It was used to describe the level of instructional competence, stress-coping styles, and work performance of newly-hired teachers when taken as a whole. This study also used the quantitative descriptive design utilizing the survey method through survey questionnaires.

Respondents

According to Canales (2018), the population refers to the entire group of people, events, or things of interest for which the researcher wants to make inferences. The total population of secondary public schools' newly hired teachers with 2-5 years of tenure from the municipalities of Pulupandan, Valladolid, San Enrique, and Pontevedra is One Hundred One (101). Since total enumeration was used in this study, therefore no sampling technique was employed.

Instrument

In this study, respondents answered questions through questionnaires. The first instrument was adapted from the study of Lebeco (2022) for the Work Instructional Competence, and a modified questionnaire for Stress Coping Styles was used which had undergone validity and reliability properly validated by experts. The research instruments used for the first part was a standardized questionnaire adapted from the study of Lebeco (2022) for Instructional Competence with a reliability index of 0.83. Thus, the researcher no longer conducted validity and reliability tests for this questionnaire. For the second part, the researcher adapted and modified a questionnaire from the study of Lin (2020) to assess the level of stress-coping styles of the newly-hired secondary teachers. For the questionnaire to be both valid and reliable, questions were constructed and validated properly by three experts using Good and Scates Validity test.

For content validity, three experts were asked to rate each question in the questionnaire as "excellent", "very good", "good", "fair" or "poor". To make a preliminary assessment of the validity and reliability of the questionnaire and to correct as many errors and omissions as possible it is necessary to conduct a pilot study with a relatively small number of participants. A reliability index of 0.8006 is the result of the test conducted with 30 respondents.

The survey instrument was divided into three parts. The first part pertained to the demographics of the respondents including age, sex, marital status, highest educational attainment and length of service of the newly-hired secondary teachers. The second part is the

assessment of the level of instructional competence using a five-point Likert scale of the respondents using the 4 level scales: lesson planning, delivery, evaluation of student's performance, and classroom management. The third part of the survey questionnaire investigated the level of stress coping styles which includes the active emotional coping, passive emotional coping, active problem coping, and problem passive coping of newly-hired secondary teachers. The respondents are asked to rate each of these parts using a five-point Likert-type scale.

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Procedure

Since the validity and reliability of the research instruments were confirmed, the data-gathering procedure was thoroughly executed. Initially, the researcher drafted a formal letter to conduct the study from the Research Adviser, and the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Division of Negros Occidental, seeking permission to conduct the questionnaire administration among the newly-hired secondary teachers within the educational institution. The letter provided a comprehensive overview of the study's objectives, methodology, and anticipated benefits, emphasizing the significance of their approval for the successful execution of the research.

Upon obtaining the necessary permissions, the researchers prepared the questionnaires for distribution. But since the participants were no longer available in their stations for the conduct of the study, the researcher utilized the google forms to gather data from the respondents. Participants received a detailed communication elucidating the study's purpose, methodology, and ethical considerations. This communication emphasized the voluntary nature of participation, assuring respondents of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. Furthermore, participants were provided with clear instructions on how to access and complete the questionnaire at their convenience, ensuring optimal response rates and data quality. Subsequently, the data were collected by the researcher as soon as the respondent has accomplished it to secure confidentiality of data and their information.

After gathering all the data, the researcher started a thorough process of data analysis. To begin with, descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation, and frequencies were calculated to provide an overview of the data and offer some initial insights into response distribution. Then, after consulting with a statistician, the proper statistical methods were used for additional data treatment, allowing for a thorough investigation and interpretation of the results. The objective of this data collection and analysis methodology was to guarantee the validity, trustworthiness, and credibility of the research findings.

Data Analysis

After the data was gathered, the researcher tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted it. Different statistical tools were used in the analyses and interpretation of data.

To answer problem no. 1, what is the demographic profile of newly hired public school teachers when grouped according to sex, age, highest educational attainment, and length of service, mean and percent distribution were used.

To answer problem no. 2's statement, what is the level of instructional competence of the respondents when grouped according to the aforementioned variables, mean, was used.

To answer the question of problem no. 3, what is the level of stress coping styles of the respondents when grouped according to the aforementioned variables, mean, frequency and standard deviation were used.

To answer problem no. 4, which states the respondents' level of work performance when grouped according to the aforementioned variables, mean, frequency, and standard deviation were used.

To answer the statement of problem no. 5, whether there is a significant difference in the level of instructional competence of teachers based on the demographic profile of the respondents, Kruskal-Wallis was used.

To answer the statement of problem no. 6, which states there is a significant difference in the level of stress coping styles of teachers in terms of the demographic profile of the respondents, Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis were used

To answer the statement of problem no. 7, which states there is a significant relationship between instructional competence and the work performance of newly hired secondary teachers, Goodman's and Kruskal Gamma were used.

To answer the statement of problem no. 8, which states there is a significant relationship between stress coping styles and the work

performance of newly hired secondary teacher, , Goodman's and Kruskal Gamma were used.

Ethical Considerations

The participants were fully informed about the purpose, risks, and benefits of the study, and provided their consent prior to participation. All personal and identifiable information of participants was also kept confidential and anonymous. All data collected was anonymized to protect participant identities and was stored securely and protected from unauthorized access. Every effort was made to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data collected. The study was designed to minimize harm or risk to participants and were not coerced or pressured into participating in the study. All sources used in the study were properly cited and referenced and the study was an original work and did not plagiarize or copy from other sources.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the interpretation of the statistically-treated data and in-depth discussions about the study. The data were arranged in tabular order as reflected in the study's specified problems.

Demographic Profile of Respondents

This section delves into crucial aspects such as age, sex, civil status, job position, and tenure offering insights into the diverse backgrounds of the study respondents.

Table 1. Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex	Male	26	25.70
	Female	75	74.30
	Total	101	100.00
Age	21-30	79	78.20
	31-40	21	20.80
	41-50	1	1.00
	51-60	0	0.00
	Over 60	0	0.00
	Total	101	100.00
Marital Status	Single	67	66.30
	Married	34	33.70
	Widowed	0	0.00
	Divorced/Separated	0	0.00
	Total	101	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	65	64.40
	With Masteral Units	25	24.80
	Master's Degree	9	8.90
	With Doctorate Units	0	0.00
	Doctorate Degree	2	2.00
	Total	101	100.00

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. The demographic profile of the respondents is divided into five categories: age, sex, marital status, highest educational attainment, and length of service. Most of the respondents are female, totaling 75 respondents (74.30%), while the male respondents have only 26 (25.70%) respondents. Appertaining to the age variable, the bracket with the highest number of respondents is 21-30 years old with 79 (78.20%) respondents, followed by 31-40 years old with 21 (21.80%) respondents and 41-50 years old with only one (1%) respondent. Meanwhile, the brackets 51-60 (0%) and over 60 (0%) have no reported respondents.

There is a noticeable margin between the number of respondents when classified according to their marital status. The data stated that 66.30% (67) of the respondents are single while only 33.70% (34) are married. Akin to the situation stipulated above with the last two bracket classifications, there were no reported respondents in the Widowed (0%) and Divorced/Separated (0%) brackets, respectively.

In terms of the highest educational attainment, an appreciable number of respondents only attained a bachelor's degree, with 65 (64.40%) of the total number of respondents. 25 (24.80%) respondents have attained their master's degree, while 2 (2%) have Doctoral Degrees. All respondents in terms of the length of service were classified in the 1-5 years bracket, equating to 101 (100%) respondents in terms of totality. The rest of the brackets, namely: 6-10 years, 11-15 years, and over 15 years, have no reported respondents (0%).

Level of instructional competence of the respondents when taken as a whole.

The instructional competence of educators can be chiefly categorized based on the areas necessary to attaining the learning outcomes set forth by the Department of Education. The analysis of this table defined the instructional competence of the respondents in the

following areas: Lesson Planning, Delivery, Evaluation of Student Performance, and Classroom Management. Table 2 presents the data and its interpretation.

Table 2. *Level of instructional competence of the respondents when taken as a whole*

<i>Instructional Competence</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Lesson Planning	101	4.38	Excellent
Delivery	101	4.49	Excellent
Evaluation of Student's Performance	101	4.37	Excellent
Classroom Management	101	4.57	Excellent
As a whole	101	4.45	Excellent

Table 2 indicates the different indicators of instructional competence of the respondents and when taken as a whole. The indicators included were evaluated individually and were analyzed.

The mean in lesson planning is 4.38, which was interpreted as excellent. This showed that the respondents' mastery of planning their lessons in written form is exemplary. This interpretation can be attributed to effective teaching methods and strategies and appropriate selection and preparation of instructional materials to fully cater to the formulated objectives that can be related to the previous knowledge or skills discussed.

In terms of delivery, the mean score is 4.49, which is also interpreted as Excellent. This suggests that the respondents can foster a higher level of thinking through the utilization of the art of questioning. Moreover, this interpretation also connotes proper voice modulation, providing appropriate motivation while conveying ideas clearly.

As reflected in the table, the Evaluation of Pupils' Performance is also interpreted as Excellent, with a mean value of 4.37. The result determined that the respondents can effectively diagnose the learners' needs, with students showing lesson mastery. Furthermore, the interpretation also ascertained that the respondents have strong perceived expertise in evaluating learning outcomes and assessing lessons.

The interpretation of classroom management is the same as the previous instructional competence indicators. The mean value is 4.57 and is interpreted as excellent. This means the respondents can maintain student interaction and rapport while utilizing positive control, discipline, and positive classroom climate.

When all of the indicators are taken together, the mean value is 4.45, which is interpreted as excellent. This result indicates that the respondents have strong instructional competence in the respective areas stated above.

The findings of this study showed similar results to those of Blömeke et al. (2022), which states that teachers have high perceived standards in terms of instructional competence in the educational setting.

Level of Stress Coping Styles of The Respondents

This section further determines the respondents' stress coping styles. The table below provides a closer look at the coping styles of respondents in terms of active emotional, passive emotional, active problem, and passive problems when taken as a whole.

Table 3. *Level of Stress Coping Styles of The Respondents*

<i>Stress Coping Styles</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Active Emotional Coping	101	4.37	Very High
Passive Emotional Coping	101	1.60	Very Low
Active Problem Coping	101	3.96	High
Passive Problem Coping	101	2.62	Moderate
As a whole	101	3.13	Moderate

Table 3 depicts the different stress coping styles of the respondents, together with their interpretations. regarding active emotional coping, the mean is 4.37, which is interpreted as very high. The result suggests that the respondents have established active coping strategies such as positive thinking and stress communication.

Moreover, the passive emotional coping result reported a mean value of 1.60, which has a very low interpretation. This means that respondents do not allow negative thoughts to hinder their ability to think rationally, thus dealing with stress effectively.

In the area of active emotional coping, the result was interpreted as high, with a mean value of 3.97, while passive emotional coping scored a mean of 2.62, which is interpreted as moderate. Both results undermine the idea that the respondents have higher positive emotional coping than their counterparts. This means that the respondents are actively looking for solutions most of the time rather than leaving aside the problems and solving them later.

The table 4 identifies the respondents' performance levels when grouped according to their demographic profile. It highlights the comprehensive interpretation based on the gathered data.

Table 4. *Level of work Performance of the respondents when grouped according to the variables*

Profile	Category	f	Mean	Interpretation
Sex	Male	26	4.50	Outstanding
	Female	75	4.46	Very Satisfactory
Age	21-30	79	4.47	Very Satisfactory
	31-40	21	4.48	Very Satisfactory
	41-50	1	4.77	Very Satisfactory
	51-60	0		
	Over 60	0		
Marital Status	Single	67	4.45	Very Satisfactory
	Married	34	4.52	Outstanding
	Widowed	0		
Highest Educational Attainment	Divorced/Separated	0		
	Bachelor's Degree	65	4.44	Very Satisfactory
	With Masteral Units	25	4.51	Outstanding
	Master's Degree	9	4.58	Outstanding
	With Doctorate Units	0		
Length of Service	Doctorate Degree	2	4.59	Outstanding
	1-5 years	101	4.47	Very Satisfactory
	6-10 years	0		
	11-15 years	0		
	Over 15 years	0		
	As a whole	101	4.47	Very Satisfactory

The level of work performance of the respondents has five indicators as per the demographic profile. As for the sex, the male has 26 with the mean value of 4.50 and an outstanding interpretation. On the other hand, the female respondents have Very Satisfactory interpretation (mean- 4.46) from 75 of the respondents.

Referring to the age demographics, it can be noted that the age indicators 21-30 ($f=79$), 31-40 ($f=21$), and 41-50 ($f=1$) yielded the same interpretation as very satisfactory. The age indicators 51-60 and over 60 had no recorded respondents so there was no interpretation given.

According to the data presented in the Marital Status of the respondents, the data showed that the single respondents ($f=67$) attained the mean value of 4.45 which is interpreted as very satisfactory while the married respondents scored the mean of 4.52 which is outstanding. The rest of the indicators in the Marital Status, namely 1) widowed and 2) divorced/separated, have no recorded mean value for interpretation due to the lack of respondents.

In terms of educational attainment, the table showed that the respondents with Masteral Units ($f=25$, mean=4.51), Masteral Degrees ($f=9$, mean= 4.58), and Doctorate Degrees ($f=2$, mean=4.59) received an Outstanding interpretation, respectively. This result is followed by the 65 respondents with Bachelor's Degrees with a mean value of 4.44 with the Very Satisfactory interpretation. There was no recorded interpretation in the Doctoral Units. Consequently, the length of service demographics has only one interpretation due to the lack of respondents. All the respondents have been in service for 1-5 years. The mean value is 4.47 from 101 respondents, interpreted as very satisfactory. In the same case, as stated above, other indicators had no respondents. The data gathered as a whole showed a mean value of 4.47, which is also interpreted as very satisfactory.

Based on the findings of the study, it can be implied that higher educational attainment can lead to higher result interpretation. Although marital status can, at times, hinder one's job performance due to added responsibility, the findings of this study suggested otherwise. This is in contrast with the findings of Çemberci et al. (2022), which state that people who are married can, at times, have lower performance due to the added responsibilities of parenthood.

Moreover, this research study also analyzed data based on the respondents' level of instructional competence. Table 5 presents a more comprehensive view when the level of competence is grouped according to sex.

Table 5.1. *Difference in the level of Instructional Competence when grouped according to Sex*

Sex	n	Mean Rank
Male	26	57.48
Female	75	48.75
Total	101	

Computed value (U): 806.50

p-value: 0.189

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 5.1 present the level of instructional competence of the respondents when grouped according to sex. Most of the respondents are female, which responds to 75 respondents, while there are only 26 respondents. The mean rank for the male is 57.48 while its counterpart received 48.75 in terms of mean rank. Since the computer p-value is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis.

Accepting the H_0 means that there is no statistical significance in the level of instructional competence regarding sex. The instructional competence of both males and females is at par, and there is no distinction that sets apart the two indicators.

In addition to sex, this study also aimed to determine the level of instructional competence based on age. Table 5b below presents this data.

Table 5.2. *Difference in the level of Instructional Competence when grouped according to Age*

Age	n	Mean Rank
21-30	79	50.69
31-40	21	51.98
41-50	1	55.00
51-60	0	
Over 60	0	
Total	101	

Computed value (H): 0.05

p-value: 0.975

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 5.2 shows the level of instructional competence of the respondents based on age. Evident in the table, the data stated that the age bracket 21-30 (n=79) has a mean rank of 50.59, which is the highest of all the mean ranks in the table. The result is followed by the age bracket 41-50 (n=1) with a mean rank of 55.00 and 31-40 (n=21) with a mean value of 51.98. The remaining age brackets in the table (51-60 and Over 60) do not have mean ranks due to the lack of data to be analyzed.

The computed values are as follows: the computed value (H) at 0.05 and the p-value of the data analyzed at 0.975 led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. The decision to accept H_0 means that there is no statistical significance between the level of competence and age at the 0.05 level.

The result of this study has the same implications as the study of Marinič & Pecina (2022), which states that the aging population of teachers does not hinder their ability to provide precise classroom instruction and lesson delivery.

Table 5.3. *Difference in the level of Instructional Competence when grouped according to Marital Status*

Marital Status	n	Mean Rank
Single	67	53.25
Married	34	46.56
Widowed	0	
Divorced/Separated	0	
Total	101	

Computed value (H): 1.18

p-value: 0.277

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table above shows the findings based on the analyzed data in terms of marital status and the level of instructional competence. Based on the data, the single respondents (n=67) have a reported mean rank of 53.25, whilst the married respondents (n=34) have a lower mean rank value at 46.56. The lack of data for statistical treatment in the widowed and divorced/separated indicated the inability to solve their mean ranks, respectively.

Further analysis of data concluded that the computed value(H) is 1.18, followed by the p-value at 0.277. These results allowed the decision of the null hypothesis to be accepted. This means that there is no statistical significance between the data stipulated above at 0.05 level of significance.

In addition, one of the study's main goals is to ascertain the level of instructional competence of the respondents when grouped according to their educational attainment. Table 5d elaborates this data on closer inspection.

The table 5.4 reports the respondents' Level of Instructional Competence based on their educational attainment. The data are as follows: Respondents with a Doctorate Degree have the highest mean rank at 66.25, with 2 respondents. It is followed by those with a master's degree (n=9) at 54.61 mean rank and those With Masteral Units (n=25) at 51.54. As stated in the table, 65 respondents with only a bachelor's degree have the lowest mean rank at 49.82.

After applying statistical analysis and data treatment, it was found that the computer value (H) is 0.80 while the p-value is 0.850, which directed the decision to accept the null hypothesis. The H_0 implies that there is no statistical significance between the respondents'

highest educational attainment and their level of instructional competence.

Table 5.4. *Differences in the Level of Instructional Competence when grouped according to Educational Attainment*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Bachelor's Degree	65	49.82
With Masteral Units	25	51.54
Master's Degree	9	54.61
With Doctorate Units	0	
Doctorate Degree	2	66.25
Total	101	
Computed value (H)		: 0.80
p-value		: 0.850
Decision		: Accept Ho
Interpretation		: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

While no statistical significance was recorded according to the data, it can be noted that the respondents with a Doctorate and master's degree scored the highest mean value. This is incongruent with the findings of Hashmi et al. (2019). Their study stated that people with higher educational backgrounds are most likely to perform well compared to those with lower educational attainment in the field of classroom instruction.

This study also highlights the importance of the length of service compared to the Level of instructional competence. Table 5e presents the data based on the idea.

Table 5.5. *Difference in the Level of Instructional Competence when grouped according to Length of Service*

<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
1-5 years	101	51.00
6-10 years	0	0
11-15 years	0	0
Over 15 years	0	0
Total	101	0

Table 5.5 states the level of instructional competence when grouped according to length of service. The table only reported one mean rank in the 1-5 years (n=101) at 51.00. The lack of data in this area inhibits proper statistical treatment to conclude whether to accept or reject the null hypothesis.

This study also discusses the level of stress coping styles. Below is the table that discusses the level of coping style when grouped according to sex.

Table 6.1. *Differences in the level of coping style when grouped according to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Male	26	56.23
Female	75	49.19
Total	101	

Computed value (U): 839.00

p-value: 0.290

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 6.1 examines the data on the respondents' level of coping style when grouped according to sex. The data presents a mean rank of 56.23 for the 26 male participants, while the 75 female respondents received a mean rank of 49.19. The mean rank of the male is higher than that of its counterpart. The analyzed data determined that the computed value of 839.0 and the p-value of 0.290 support the Ho.

This means that the level of coping style when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant at 0.05 level. It can be noted that sex is not a determining factor as to the level of coping styles of the respondents. One of the study's aims is to find the level of coping styles based on age. The table below discusses this data.

The table 6.2 depicts the data concerning the level of coping style when grouped according to Age. Based on the analyzed data, it can be inferred that the age range of 31-40 (n=21) got the highest mean rank at 57.36, followed by the age range of 21-30 (n=79) with the mean rank of 49.44 and lastly, with the mean rank of 40.50 is the age range of 41-50 (n=1). The remaining age indicators have no respondents thus, no data can be used to solve the mean rank.

Further statistical evaluation showed that the computer value (H) is 1.34, while the p-value ranged at 0.511. With these statistical results, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis. There is no significance in terms of age and level of coping styles at the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 6.2. Differences in the level of coping styles when grouped according to Age

Age	n	Mean Rank
21-30	79	49.44
31-40	21	57.36
41-50	1	40.50
51-60	0	
Over 60	0	
Total	101	

Computed value (H): 1.34
 p-value: 0.511
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The findings of this study are in contrast with what is stated in the study of Kołodziejczyk et al., (2021). Their study stated that age is one of the primary factors that can affect one's coping style in relation to stress. Furthermore, they noted that the age effect "...was found to be significant in all the ANCOVA models..." in their study.

Table 6.3. Difference in the Level of Coping Styles when grouped according to Marital Status

Marital Status	n	Mean Rank
Single	67	48.93
Married	34	55.07
Widowed	0	
Divorced/Separated	0	
Total	101	

Computed value (H): 0.99
 p-value: 0.319
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table gives a clearer view of the levels of coping style in relation to marital status based on the gathered and analyzed Data.

Table 6.3 displays the data in terms of the level of stress coping styles and marital status. According to the data, the Married (n=34) got the mean rank of 55.07 which is followed by the Single (n=67) with a mean rank of 48.93 percent. The rest of the indicators under marital status have no identified respondents thus leading to the unavailability of data.

The computed value (H) is 0.99, and the p-value is 0.319. Based on these two results, the null hypothesis is accepted. The acceptance of the null hypothesis means that there is no significance between the stated variables at the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 6.4. Differences in the level of coping styles when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	n	Mean Rank
Bachelor's Degree	65	46.73
With Masteral Units	25	60.44
Master's Degree	9	47.39
With Doctorate Units	0	
Doctorate Degree	2	88.00
Total	101	

Computed value (H): 7.32
 p-value: 0.062
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 6.4 shows the level of coping styles when grouped according to the Highest Educational Attainment. The highest mean rank is Doctorate Degree (n=2) with 88.00, followed by Masteral Units (n=9) at 47.39. The said results are followed by the master's degree (n=9) indicator with a mean rank of 47.39 and the Bachelor's Degree (n=65) at 46.73. The computed value (H) according to the statistically treated data is 7.32, while the p-value is 0.062. With these results, the Ho is accepted. The acceptance of the null hypothesis means that there is no statistical significance between the level of coping styles and the Highest Educational Attainment.

Table 6.5 provides a more detailed and data-driven review of the level of coping styles regarding the Length of Service.

Table 6.5. Differences in the level of coping styles when grouped according to Length of Service

Length of Service	n	Mean Rank
1-5 years	101	51.00
6-10 years	0	
11-15 years	0	
Over 15 years	0	

Total	101
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The table above shows the data regarding the Length of Service and the level of coping styles. In this variable, only one indicator has presented data, which is the 1-5 years (n=101). In the indicator, the mean rank is 51.00. The rest of the indicators under the Length of Service have no identifiable data, thus, they cannot be statistically treated for significance.

Table 7. Relationship Between the level of Instructional Competence and the level of Work Performance of Newly Hired Secondary Teachers

Level of Instructional competence	Level of Work Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	Poor	
Excellent	40	36	3	0	0	79
Very Satisfactory	9	12	1	0	0	22
Satisfactory	0	0	0	0	0	0
Unsatisfactory	0	0	0	0	0	0
Poor	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	49	48	4	0	0	101

Computed value (G): 0.18
 p-value: 0.426
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

This study also aimed to answer how the Instructional Competence and Work Performance of newly Hired Secondary Teachers statistically respond to one another. The table below provides some valuable insight regarding this notion. The table above refers to the relationship between the level of instructional competence together with the level of work performance. The following interpretations for the level of instructional competence are as follows: Excellent, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, and Poor. In addition, the level of work performance follows the following interpretation: Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, and Poor. As presented in the table, of the 79 respondents who got an Excellent rating in the Level of Instructional awareness, 40 got Outstanding, 36 got Very Satisfactory, and 3 got a Satisfactory rating in the level of their work performance. Meanwhile, the respondents (n=22) who scored Very Satisfactory in the level of instructional competence have the following interpretation in the level of work performance: 9 got Outstanding, 12 were categorized into Very Satisfactory rating while 1 Satisfactory. There was no recorded rating in the Unsatisfactory and Poor ratings in both variables.

The computer value (H) is 0.18 while the p-value is 0.426. Based on these results, it was ascertained that there is no statistical significance between the two variables, and the Ho was accepted as the same with the implications of the study While the results prove that there is no statistical significance between the two variables, a study by Aindra (2022) proved the otherwise. The findings of their study stated that one’s instructional competence as an educator is one of the key factors in attaining excellent work performance.

Additionally, the level of coping styles and work performance are crucial in every work environment. This study’s last findings regarding the variables are presented in the table below.

Table 8. Relationship Between the Level of stress Coping Styles and the Level of Work Performance of Newly Hired Secondary Teachers

Level of Stress Coping Styles	Level of Work Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	Poor	
Very High	2	1	0	0	0	3
High	12	5	0	0	0	17
Moderate	35	41	4	0	0	80
Low	0	1	0	0	0	1
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	49	48	4	0	0	101

Computed value (G): 0.52
 p-value: 0.013
 Decision: Reject Ho
 Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table above presents the data about the relationship between the level of stress coping styles and the level of work performance of the newly hired secondary teachers. As reflected in the table, the respondents with Very High levels of stress coping styles have scored Outstanding (n=2) and Very Satisfactory (n=1) in the level of work performance. Additionally, the respondents with High level of stress coping style have scored 12 in the Outstanding indicator and 5 in Very Satisfactory.

The first two indicators have no recorded data at the lower levels. Relative to the above ideas, the respondents with moderate levels of stress coping styles have scored as follows: 41 in the Very Satisfactory interpretation, 35 in Outstanding, and 4 in Satisfactory. Consequently, the only reported respondent with a low level of stress coping style (n=1) has a Very Satisfactory level of work performance. No data was recorded in the lower levels of the aforementioned indicators.

The computed value (G) is 0.52 while the p-value based on the analyzed data is 0.013. The statistically treated data suggest that the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected. There is a statistical relationship between the two variables at a 0.05 level of significance. The result

of this study is supported by the study of . . . which stated one's level of work performance can be determined based on one's ability to cope with stress. A higher ability in stress management is essential in providing quality work performance Pflieger (2021).

Conclusions

The study reveals that newly hired educators possess excellent instructional competence, very low passive emotional thinking, and very high active emotional coping. Their overall work performance is deemed very satisfactory.

The absence of a significant relationship between instructional competence, stress coping styles, and demographic profile suggests that other factors may influence these variables. However, a significant relationship was found between stress coping styles and work performance, indicating that healthy stress coping habits can positively impact work performance.

Nurture Healthy Stress-Coping Habits: Encourage and support newly hired educators in developing and maintaining healthy stress-coping mechanisms.

Explore Other Influencing Factors: Investigate other variables that may impact instructional competence, stress coping styles, and work performance.

Provide Ongoing Support: Offer continuous support and resources to newly hired educators to enhance their instructional competence, stress management, and overall work performance.

References

- Adelman, N. E. (2021). *Preservice training and continuing professional development of teachers*. Washington, D.C: Policy Studies Associates.
- Aliakbari, M., & Heidarzadi, M. (2020). The relationship between EFL teachers' beliefs and actual practices of classroom management. *Cogent Education*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2015.1039255>
- Alliance for Excellent Education. (2019). *On the path to equity: Improving the effectiveness of beginning teachers*. Retrieved from <http://all4ed.org/wpcontent/uploads/2019/07/PathToEquity.pdf>
- Al-Mahrooqi, R., Denman, C., Al-Siyabi, J. & Al-Maamari, F. (2020). Characteristics of a good EFL teacher: omani EFL teacher and student perspectives. *SAGE Open*, 5, 1-15. <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/2158244015584782>
- Aindra, A. D., Wibawa, A. P., & Nurhadi, D. (2022). Teacher's competence and performance: A systematic theoretical study. *International Journal of Education and Learning*, 4(1), 65–80. <https://doi.org/10.31763/ijelev.v4i1.397>
- Andersen, N. E. (2020). *Preservice training and continuing professional development of teachers*. Washington, D.C: Policy Studies Associates.
- Barnuevo, RJ U., Hasegawa, K. B., & Hugo, E. (2020). *Instructional Competencies Of The Teaching Force Their Relationship To The Students Academic Performance*.
- Bastürk, S., & Tastepe, M. (2020). Examining primary pre-service teachers' difficulties of mathematics teaching with the microteaching method. *Acta Didactica Napocensia*, 8(3), 1-10.
- Bellinger, H.W. (2022). *Education watch state summaries*. Washington, D.C.: Education Trust.
- Berry, B., Hopkins-Thompson, T., & Hoke, M. (2022). *Assessing and supporting new teachers: Lessons from the Southeast*. North Carolina. The Southeast Center for Teaching Quality at the University of North Carolina.
- Biernal, A. L. (2021). *New teacher induction: How to train, support, and retain new teachers*. Mountain View, CA: Harry K. Wong Publications, Inc.
- Blackless, D. A. (2021). The design and administration of surveys. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 17, 225–249.
- Blömeke, S., Jentsch, A., Ross, N., Kaiser, G., & König, J. (2022). Opening up the black box: Teacher competence, instructional quality, and students' learning progress. *Learning and Instruction*, 79, 101600. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2022.101600>
- Bodine, R.J. (2020). School climate and social-emotional learning: Predicting teacher stress, job satisfaction, and teaching efficacy. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 104(4), 1189-1204. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0029356>
- Bornstein, L. A. (2020). *Effective teaching and mentoring: Realizing the transformational power of adult learning experiences*. San Francisco:
- Canales, A. (2018). Teacher quality and student achievement in Chile: Linking teachers' contribution and observable characteristics. *International Journal of Educational Development*, vol. 60, pp. 33-50, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ijedudev.2017.09.009.
- Chen, S. (2022). Predictive roles of thinking styles in coping strategies among mainland postgraduate students in Hong Kong. *Frontiers*

in Psychology, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.693637>

Chao, C. N. G., Chow, E. W. S., Forlin, C., & Ho, F. C. (2022). Improving teachers' self-efficacy in applying teaching and learning strategies and classroom management to students with special education needs in Hong Kong. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 66, 360–369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.05.004>

Department of Education (2018). The K to 12 Education Program (Discussion Group). Retrieved September 29, 2022 from <http://www.deped.gov.ph/k-12/>.

Feiman-Nemser, S. (2021). From preparation to practice: Designing a continuum to strengthen and sustain teaching. *Teachers College Record*, 103(6), 1013–1055. doi:10.1111/0161-4681.00141.

Gipson, C. R. (2021). The perception of beginning teachers regarding the mentoring program in Mississippi public schools (Doctoral dissertation). Mississippi College.

Harmsen, R.; Helms-Lorenz, M. (2019). The longitudinal effects of induction on beginning teachers' stress. *Br.J. Educ. Psychol.* 89, 259–287.

Kaur, M., & Talwar, A. (2019). Teaching Competency of Secondary School Teachers in Relation to Emotional Intelligence. *International Journal of Learning*

Kidger, J. (2021). Teachers' wellbeing and depressive symptoms, and associated risk factors: A large cross-sectional study in English secondary schools. *J. Affect. Disord.* 192,76–82.

Lebeco, G. G. (2022). *Teaching and the teacher*. Manila: Lorimar Publishing Company, Inc.

Lin, R. W. & Hackett, G. (2020). Career self-efficacy: Empirical status and future directions. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 30, 347-382.

Luft, J. A., & Dubois, S. L. (Eds.). (2020). *Newly hired teachers of science: A better beginning*. Springer.

Maslach, C. (2023). Job burnout: New directions in research and intervention. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 12(5), 189–192. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8721.01258>

Marinič, P., & Pecina, P. (2022). Age structure of teachers in selected EU countries. *INTED2022 Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.21125/inted.2022.2090>

Obispo, R. T., Magulod Jr., G. C., & Tindowen, D. J. C. (2021). Teachers' classroom management styles and student- teacher connectedness and anxiety. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(5), 123–141. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.20.5.7>

Ornstein, A. C. & Lunenburg, F. C. (2018). *Educational Administration: Concepts and Practices*. Thomson Higher Education.

Pfleging, A. C. (2021). Confronting the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic: A quantitative analysis of the relationships among secondary teachers' perceived resilience, trait emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy. *Manhattanville College*.

Popescu, M., Cirja, A., & Duminica, A. (2019). Stress and Coping Strategies among Teachers in Gymnasium Schools. *Journal of Experiential Psychotherapy*, 22(86).

Stapleton, P., Garby, S., & Sabot, D. (2020). Psychological distress and coping styles in teachers: A preliminary study. *Australian Journal of Education*, 64(2), 127-146.

Sultan, S., & Shafi, M. (2019). Impact of Perceived Teachers' Competence On Students' Performance: Evidence for Mediating/Moderating Role of Class Environment. *I-manager's Journal on Educational Psychology*, 8, 10-18.

Watt, H. & Richardson, P. (2022). Motivational factors influencing teaching as a career choice: Development and validation of the FIT-Choice scale. *Journal of Experimental Education*, 75, 167–202.

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